

BIOGENIC DATA FORMS

Emergent Mapping for Novel Form-Finding Processes

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ABSTRACT

'Mapping' as a bridging mechanism between science and digital design, provides a theoretical and experimental framework for the proposed biological-data-driven workflow (Schoonderbeek, 2021). Understanding the concept of animate architecture, the complexities of extracellular polymeric substances as systems, and the origins of mapping, was a critical departure point for this work. The research coupled a series of lab experimentations on the environmental stress response of the cyanobacteria, *Oscillatoria animalis*, extracellular polymeric substances [EPS], and the corresponding growth data sets with computational simulations. The stress responses were initiated by a change in the culture's pH levels. Data were conveyed through negative-gram staining, anatomized through ImageJ pixel analysis, and translated into a set of particles in Houdini. Further attributes were applied to the set, matching the particle count to the size of the cell colony and the diameter to the frequency of colony size, and using trail length to represent the colony aging. The final result is a digital simulation able to produce digital models and animations driven by biological data that were acquired through laboratory experiments with living cells. By translating lab data into three-dimensional visualizations, this workflow is a dynamic tool for the creative mapping of microbial data within the realm of architectural design.

1. INTRODUCTION

Extracellular polymeric substances [EPS] hold great potential as biological indicators of environmental conditions. EPS serves as an indication of environmental stress factors such as nutrient deprivation, salinity, agitation, light exposure, and pH (Flemming et al., 2016). A significant role of extracellular polymeric substances [EPS] is to act as a protectant for the cell, regulating the internal cell body through an intermediate buffer zone to the surrounding environment as it envelops the perimeter of the cell wall (Karygianni et al., 2020). This secretion of extracellular polysaccharides serves as a protective barrier for both the cells of the cyanobacteria and matrix-housed bacteria (Flemming et al., 2016). Symbiotic relationships are formed within the matrix, leading to the complexity of functions, responsiveness, and biofilm formation. Recognizing the polymer network as a scaffold, they form a ‘microbial city,’ likened the biogenic formation to that of the Anthropocene, argued to be the most prevalent lifestyle of microorganisms in the biosphere (Flemming et al., 2016; Karygianni et al., 2020). By regulating and visualizing the biofilm precursor of extracellular polymeric substances, a more comprehensive understanding of their potential within the field of the biological sciences could be achieved (Howard, 1994; Potysz & Bartz, 2022; Priester et al., 2007).

‘Morphogenetic Architecture’ describes a design methodology based on biological principles through computational representation, where the emergence and evolutionary development of a specimen form, or part thereof, is central (Korra, 2018). Similarly, bio-integrated design’s interlaced parameters for the constructs of form and function over time in varied degrees of agency with nature, posit the traditional binaries of ecology and architecture blurred. As Leon Krier’s conceptual framework, *The 6th Order or The End of Architecture*, 1977, critiqued architecture of his time, proposing a Post-Modern order to the architectural canon, perhaps here too we are at a time where a ‘7th Order’ is at hand; one of the bio-digital frontier amongst the umbrellaing categorization of ‘Emergent Architecture’ embracing emergent technologies and biological paradigms (Hensel et al., 2010).

Animate Architecture is defined by the co-presence of motion and force at the moment of formal conception, utilizing animation software beyond rendering to find architectural form (Elshanwany et al., 2020). Force as an initial condition changes the atmosphere, which affects both motion and particular inflections of the form (Elshanwany et al., 2020). Where the principle of the terminology stays constant, bio-integrated design’s approach towards

the dynamism of nature calls for new considerations of architectural norms and design by the inclusion of the needs of all inhabitants in concomitance. Current advancements in the field of tools, methods, and technology, allow designers to step away from traditional problem-solving thinking and move towards a creative and imaginative engagement with nature (Armstrong, 2018).

Mapping, as an instrumentalization, operationalization, or conceptualization of the spatial map, operates in the understanding that mapping of architecture has the potential for this transfer of data to a visualized form (Schoonderbeek, 2017). Historically, the term originated as a mathematical term that allows for a relational description of space and time rather than strictly metric or chronological (Schoonderbeek, 2017). Now, with the adaptation of cartography and topology, the mode of synthesis involves social sciences, spatial conditions, and the various forms of mapping, including the practices of postmodern mapping, subversive, counter-mapping, thematic, critical, and that which dissolve and reform in contemporary art practices (Schoonderbeek, 2021). As a tool in practicum, mapping is the process of translation, situating time, space, and relation (Hall, 2012). In similar reckonings, utilizing lab/biological data in contemporary scientific practice seeks novel communication tools. In a non-exhaustive review, mapping considers the prescribed subject's direction, scale, framing, legend, narrative, documentation, and reduced reality (Hall, 2012). Whereas in the sciences, experimentation variables/controls, protocols, hypothesis review, results evaluation, and contextualized discussion operate in similar ways for experimentation with information being communicated through diagrammatic synthesis. Visualizing what is typically unseen enables the experimentation to be recorded and translated, setting the biological premise for an Animate Architecture form-finding exploration. Therefore, it is worth reconsidering the current frameworks of digital design and scientific experimentation and attempting to define this emergent realm of design thinking and working.

This paper presents a workflow for form generation through a creative mapping process. The initial data set, that derives from lab experimentation, informs a computational simulation, as summarized in Figure 1. In the context of this research, lab experiments are focused on an indirect quantification of the cyanobacteria, *Oscillatoria*'s acidification response, and stimuli to yield the greatest EPS and biomass formation. The proposed workflow translates the aforementioned lab data of EPS growth and acidification, into digital representations and animations.

Figure 1:
Intersecting terminology
 concerning digital
 morphogenesis in the
 architectural canon further
 developed (Elshanwany et al.,
 2020) comparative analysis
 of digital morphogenesis
 techniques (Diagram
 Translation: Author, 2024).

2. METHODOLOGY

The Oscillatoria cultures were cultivated in standard BG-11 growth media with supplemented trace elements with the liquid media pH adjusted to [4, 5, 6, 7, 9] with HCl and NaOH respectively. A droplet of the Winsor & Newton India ink allowed for the visualization of the complete biomass surface area [Figure 2], including the released EPS network as seen in Figures 3 and 4.

Samples of different liquid media pH levels were analysed as seen in Figures 5 and 6. The EPS network was then translated digitally through ImageJ analysis and a Houdini particle trail simulation to achieve the proposed bio-digital mapping workflow. Particle trail growth simulations were rendered in Houdini software through an algorithm that correlates lab experiment parameters to digital simulation parameters.

Figure 2:
Annotated microscopy slide
visualizing biomass and
released EPS matrix (Author,
2023).

Figure 3:
Counter-stained
cyanobacteria Oscillatoria,
featuring a haloing perimeter
of the surrounding EPS
network (Author, 2023).

Figure 4:
**Diagrammatic identification
 of counter-stained
 cyanobacteria Oscillatoria**
 (Author, 2023).

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After two weeks of growth inside a growth chamber on an orbital shaker at 60RPM, the biomass samples were isolated by centrifugation, separating the cells from the supernatant, following methanol-cell fixation on a microscopy slide. The data to be mapped are extrapolated through microscopy images from the negative staining of fixed cells on a microscopy slide, following the methods described by Borah et al. for the visualization of microbial extracellular polymeric substances [EPS] concerning innate microbial response to the environmental stress of pH change.

Figure 5:
Influence of pH ranges on Oscillatoria, featuring the pH 6 microscopy slide with increased EPS formation (Author, 2023).

ImageJ analysis measured the counterstained samples' collective surface area [biomass and EPS]. Threshold filters were applied, transferring the image into a binary black and white at different intensities, allowing for pixel analysis. A yellow bounding box indicated the area of consideration, which can be standardized shapes or manually outlined. Using the 'Otsu' threshold primarily, an algorithm that searches for a threshold that minimizes the intra-class variance, each image was individually adjusted to indicate the visible biomass (Otsu, 1979). Calculating the biomass surface area was achieved through the difference of the 'Otsu' and 'Default' threshold settings.

Figure 6: Pigmented fibril biomass seen interlaced amongst a web-like network of polymers on the outlying edges of the pH 7 Oscillatoria sample increased in magnification (Author, 2024)

Optimization of histogram pixel analysis was done to measure the surface area of biomass as compared to the released polymers/EPS through the weighing hue, saturation, and brightness peaks from acidification tracking of bromophenol blue dye, as seen in Figure 8 comparative to the initial biomass pixel selection of Figure 7.

Figure 7: ImageJ pixelation analysis for an agar plate at 8-bit color adjustment, threshold type: Otsu with tailored adjustment, the yellow bounding box of the analysis area, and a sample of the resulting Excel output; and visual comparison of omitted tendril quantification of the threshold analysis due to labeling and casted shadow (Author, 2023).

After the quantification of surface area to pixel islands was established, it was then correlated to a point cloud in Houdini, by importing a CSV file from the ImageJ analysis. A particle trails algorithm was chosen after analyzing Geesey's electron microscopy images, which indicated a fibrillar understanding of the polymer network.

After surveying the area 'Minimum' (1.00) and 'Maximum' (varied), varying as to the size of the collective biomass, the total number of particles was reduced to 1000 entries, prioritizing the larger pixel clusters. The omissions derived from the single-pixel islands as they were the bulk of the data results. Single-pixel islands correlated to having the smallest surface area. So, excluding them from the dataset became essential to maintaining a workable file for a standard commercial laptop.

Figure 8: Refined quantification methodology for ImageJ pixel analysis for colored plates utilizes both the 'color' and 'standard' threshold filters. Gaining a more granular pixel surface area analysis amongst hue variation exemplified by an *A.niger* on bromophenol blue agar plate. The yellow tonality visualizes unlocked and available phosphorus as a part of synthetic lichen experimentation.

The developed Houdini algorithm combines a color-based attribute map of the analyzed image and a 'for each' solver to handle the imported data from the pixel islands. The microscopy image was projected onto a spherical surface, in an attempt to represent the EPS network growth in liquid media, in a digital three-dimensional space. The particle trails were specified by diameters that derived from the frequency of colony size, and trail length. Houdini VOP and attribute wrangles were used to visualize the growth digitally.

Figure 9:
Workflow from microscopy image to applied data mapping ending with a still frame of a growth simulation of different experimentation samples.

3. RESULTS

The presented workflow results in a data-driven visualization and speculative growth simulation of the *Oscillatoria* cyanobacteria cultures. The data driving this process are extrapolated from physical lab experiments and are used as a base for the initiation of the creative mapping process.

Figure 9 outlines a comparative set of results deriving from the presented workflow for three microscopy samples. It highlights the variety of resulting forms as well as the impact and therefore the importance of each decision made between each step of the process. Similar to the process of mapping, the design here becomes an interplay between data handling and data omission.

Given that there is no singular method of exercising Animate Architecture through the lens of living architecture and bio-integrated design, we propose a highly customizable workflow as a tool to navigate data extrapolation, analysis, and computational application. From the extraction of a database from the lab experiments to the parameters of the digital algorithm, each step calls for active decision-making that will affect the final form. In that way, this workflow is a tool to help designers express their design thinking, and work in a much less linear and way more interlacing manner.

The proposed workflow is an agile and customizable creative tool. A set of design decisions regarding the generation of the original particle group, scale, and trail length allows users to explore multiple form-finding paths. These design decisions can be made through the controllable parameters that have been introduced in this workflow. Furthermore, the proposed data handling method of omitting certain inputs to generate the final particle set contributes to the democratization and accessibility of tools and processes. It achieves that by allowing more users to run the proposed simulation without needing access to a supercomputer.

While this form-finding workflow describes a unique bridging between lab and computational data, numerous potentials could be further explored. From the lab experimentation setup to the decisions made while processing, transferring, mapping, and refining parameters and data, to the chosen animation variables (ie. spherical form, particle trail), there is merit in every step of this mapping process. Specifically, in the context of the Houdini algorithm, a notable design opportunity exists to layer a series of analyzed images of a single living organism over a set duration or to create a digital twin of the physical experimentation where micro-relations can be monitored in real-time through a corresponding dynamic animation. A progressional animated timelapse of the microbial growth could be rendered by staggering the corresponding data files over a comparable timeline tracking alongside other staining types of varying saturation peaks.

4. DISCUSSION

By embracing the paradoxical relationships of what is natural and what is man-made, traditionally binary boundaries become subversively blurred. Application of digital simulations scaled to the microbial level, bridges computation and lab within novel realms and scales of computational-aided design. This design is multi-scalar. Beyond form, Flemming's allegory of the EPS as a microbial city illustrates the potential of techno-biotic relations, with the potential to transcend engineered mutualism from Petri to building scale. Such a design approach can lead to the deliberate formation of what Armstrong describes as natural condensations that are site-specific and create niches throughout the built environment. (2018, pp.24)

Considering architectural and urban scales, the presented workflow has a range in applicability where nature-related growth factors [ie. pH] could support sustainable and low-impact microbial microclimate design methodologies for cyanobacteria and other microbial phyla including algae, fungi, and flora. By cross-referencing optimal environments with localized water cycling and solar radiation data sets, microbial partnerships for biogenic greening are enacted.

The notion of extending environmental analysis for optimal building design/efficiencies in consideration of the microbial scale could also lead to new territories for the natural sequestering of carbon by optimizing the environment in which particular ecologies flourish and/or perform efficacy function. Extending such research to the built environment holds the potential to not only influence the performance of the structure and building materials but also impact the localized ecosystems, through the increase and protection of biodiversity, rehabilitation of damaged ecologies, and fostering natural urban greening.

Given the customizable nature of the presented workflow, different types of lab experiment data could be extracted and utilized in form-finding processes. Data extraction has the potential to extend beyond the microbial scale towards the built environment and could include amongst others surveying nutrient profiling of materials, bioinformatics for multi-species inhabitation, or biogeochemical seasonal nutrient cycles. This broadens the types of data that are being used currently in such processes and reintroduces data sets that have been disregarded as non-related. These sets could now come into play as designing across scales introduces greater granularity of growth/performance influences. Therefore tools that allow users to handle this complexity are necessary when working with bio-digital systems.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Elshanwany's positioning of 'Alive Architecture' has been approached as the precipice of the presented theoretical framework for research. This research attempts to move further from the ideas of Metabolism towards a design realm that co-creates with dynamic, living systems. By bringing data-centric relations to the center, it aims to provide a tool for users to explore the concepts of mapping physical information in the digital space and creatively visualizing laboratory data. Designing as such then expands the architectural form-finding process while crafting a built environment in greater intimacy amongst situated ecologies, aiding understandings of the complexities of biogenic phenomena, leading eventually to the successful integration of the living with the man-made.

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